

THE ISSUE OF STYLE IN RELIGIOUS TEXTS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE
(IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE WORK OF SHEIKH MUHAMMAD SADIQ
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Abstract. *In this article, the style of religious texts, which has been an integral part of the styles of the Uzbek language for many years, is studied on the example of the book called "Hadith and hayot". During the article, the author's ability to use of specific language expressions is revealed.*

Key words: *"Hadith va hayot" language style, styles, religious texts, N.A. Baskakov, influence of Islam, religious style.*

ПРОБЛЕМА СТИЛЯ В РЕЛИГИОЗНЫХ ТЕКСТАХ НА УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ
(НА ПРИМЕРЕ РАБОТЫ ШЕЙХА МУХАММАДА САДИКА МУХАММАДА
ЮСУФА)

Аннотация. *В этой статье стиль религиозных текстов, который на протяжении многих лет был неотъемлемой частью стилей узбекского языка, изучается на примере книги под названием "Хадисы и хайот". В ходе статьи раскрывается способность автора к использованию специфических языковых выражений.*

Ключевые слова: *языковой стиль "Хадис ва хайот", стили, религиозные тексты, Н.А. Баскаков, влияние ислама, религиозный стиль.*

Hadith is the second important source after the Qur'an, another support in the faith of believers. The Qur'an, which serves as the main program in our religion, was revealed by Allah to our Prophet, and if it was a light that fell into the hearts of that person, it was the responsibility of our Prophet to spread that light to the hearts of other Muslim people. That is why our Prophet, peace and blessings of God be upon him, gave interpretations of the actions mentioned in the Qur'an. For example, if our main source says that it is obligatory to pray, they have told and shown in detail how to pray. In addition, it is considered Sunnah to describe the actions of the Companions, the things they said in different situations, the approval of the events committed by their close friends, the narrations about that person's manners, and the information describing the blessed ways of life. It is said that the words Sunnah and Hadith are used interchangeably by the Sheikh . That is, "Hadith" is from the Arabic word meaning words, meaning the words of our Prophet . "Sunnah" is also an Arabic word that means the way of life . From this it can be understood that the deeds and words of our Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, which he showed as correct during his life, are united in the two words mentioned above. If we look carefully at the meaning of the terms, it is more appropriate to use hadith as the second source term, while Sunnat has a more general meaning.

The style of texts in the Uzbek language is always unique. For example, the artistic and journalistic style incorporates imagery, emotionality, and similes, while the official and scientific styles are much more limited in this regard, and it is important that the information given in them is simple, concise, and fluent. The religious style of the texts included in the list of these styles is characterized by the fact that they have important signs. However, none of the sources mention

anything about the religious style of the Uzbek language, and N.A. Baskakov did not go beyond the idea that there is a religious style in the Uzbek language. In the monograph "O'zbek tili funksional stilistikasi" by S. Karimov, he limited himself to the opinion that "However, the issue of whether the religious style really exists in the Uzbek language, and if so, what are its linguostylistic features, has not yet been studied". Taking this into account, because the activity of Arabic revolutions and the weight of the author's speech are clearly visible in the text style of religious works in Uzbek language created in our country, Ph.D. Sh.R. Omonturdiyeva also conducted research on this issue. According to her research she says "Words and sentences expressing religious concepts and ideas were used in our language even before Islam. Over time, only a certain part of them has been preserved. As the influence of Islam increased more and more, our language was enriched with words and expressions related to the new doctrine".

In this regard, we can see the peculiarities of religious text styles in the example of the works of Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf.

The work "Hadith va hayot" written by Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf is distinguished by its popular, simple and fluent language. This work is considered a translation of Mansur Ali Nasif's hadith book "At-Tajul jame' lil usul fi ahadisur Rasul" ("The crown that collects the originals of the hadiths of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him"), and it was interpreted by the Sheikh based on today's times, without the exact translation. Special attention is paid to the fact that the book belongs to the Hanafi sect, which has been practiced in our country since ancient times. The introduction to the work begins with the sentence "Bismillahir rahmanir rohiym" and praises to Allah, blessings and peace to the Prophet, and ends with the phrase "As-salamu alaykum wa rahmatullahu wa barakatuhu". Instead, Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf followed his own style of speech, and for the sake of humility, take the shortcomings from your employee, the achievements from God, thanks be to God, praise be to God, rather, God knows, Ahamdulillah, Insha'Allah, God willing, God's He used phrases like his grace, Nauzi Billah (God save), God's will. The effectiveness of this work is the same as that of a work of art, only exaggeration, dialectics, historicisms, slang are not used. We can see this in the hadiths cited as proof of the thoughts of the Sheikh in the introduction to the work. "Praise be to Allah, the Exalted, He said in His book, "Take whatever the Prophet gives you, and whatever he turns you away from, turn back." May Allah bless the one who hears, memorizes, assimilates, and then conveys my words. It is clear from this that the whole work follows an idea, the goal of the author is a clear direction, which is characterized by the fact that the Sheikh has a unique style.

His Highness the Sheikh wrote the book "Tafsiri Hilal", which was published in Uzbek language for the first time in our country, and after it was received with high respect among the people, he mobilized to improve the spiritual path of Muslims. They say that they dared to do this after consulting with their mentors and scholars and performing Haj several times. The writing of this book was started on June 26, 1996 and finished on Wednesday, July 10, 2002. In creating this book, His Highness Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq aimed first of all at conveying the Islamic knowledge that God commanded and the Prophet said to the people. In this regard, they tried to make the language of this written work close to simple, fluent vernacular, so that both ordinary people and experts in the Islamic field could benefit from it. Thanks to this accomplishment, we can see how scholarly His Holiness Sheikh is, how important it is to spread enlightenment to people, how important it is to teach others while studying. As the name of the work indicates its

content, the hadiths from the book have been selected and adapted to current issues, problems and various controversial situations. In the process of translating the texts of the hadith from the Arabic language, Hazrat quoted the Arabic text first, and then gave the Uzbek translation and gave permissible comments on this hadith. The book consists of thirty-nine parts, and each part is dedicated to a certain topic.

These topics are relevant in the life of Muslims as a whole and serve as a great source of education for all believers of the religion. The situations for the independence of our country were prepared for such a blessed work to see the world in our country. During the time of the former Soviet Union government, any religious process was strictly regulated, and it was a very difficult task to perform such meritorious works under the control of non-religious people day and night. Nevertheless, the logical demands of Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf were fulfilled in order to improve the relationship of the Soviet Union government with other Islamic countries. A number of mosques were built and the activities of madrasas improved. But the work on the book "Hadith va hayot" and the publication of this book coincided with the first years of independence. There is no doubt that now all our compatriots will use this blessed book to learn how to act in the subtle aspects of life and strengthen our Islamic knowledge.

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